

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF AN ULTRA-LIGHTWEIGHT,
SOLID DEPLOYABLE REFLECTOR

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ABSTRACT

During the past fifteen years, Composite Optics, Incorporated, (COI), has been very successful in the aerospace industry in the design and manufacture of thermally stable structures and high-precision, lightweight, solid reflector systems. COI's latest program, the Special Sensor Microwave Imager Sounder (SSMIS) Reflector, extends its capabilities into the area of ultra-lightweight, solid, deployable reflectors. This endeavor incorporates and improves the technologies developed on the stationary reflectors with the deployment mechanism technologies while maintaining the system's thermal stability.

The SSMIS Deployable Reflector is a solid, offset paraboloid reflector with a 24-inch-diameter aperture supported from a rotating base that slowly spins the system during operation. The reflector structure is supported by two base plate deployment mechanisms and two mid-support arm release supports. The physical configuration requirement of the reflective surface is very accurate (.001 RMS), the launch frequency is high (> 100 Hz), and the weight is very low while maintaining thermal stability.

This paper addresses specific details concerning the structural design, analysis, and fabrication of the SSMIS deployable reflector. Design requirements are illustrated and candidate materials discussed. The manufacturing and analysis approach used in the design of this graphite/epoxy structure is examined in detail to illustrate the desirability of this material system and design approach in meeting design requirements.

KEYWORDS: Deployable; Reflector; Composite; Lightweight; Design.

1. INTRODUCTION

The structural development of an ultra-lightweight, solid, deployable reflector for the Special Sensor Microwave Image Sounder (SSMIS) Reflector is presented. The SSMIS, shown in Figure 1, is a major scanning component on the next generation of the DMSP Block 5D-3 (S-16 and beyond).

FIGURE 1. THE SSMIS REFLECTOR MOUNTED ON THE DMSP

It is scheduled to be launched in the mid-1990s and is being provided for the Air Force.

Figure 2 shows the placement of the deployable reflector on the SSMIS. Similar to its predecessor, the SSMI reflector, which flies on the DMSP Block 5D-3 (through S-15), the SSMIS reflector deploys from a stowed position through a 74-degree rotation about a hinge axis and operates at a range of frequencies from 19 GHz to 191 GHz while spinning at 31.6 rpm about an axis normal to the mounting platform. The major performance improvement of the SSMIS reflector over its predecessor includes significant weight savings, simpler mechanism utilization, and better thermal stability over the complete operating temperature range. The SSMIS reflector is critical to the performance of the DMSP.

Having had fifteen years of design and fabrication experience of thermally stable structures and high-precision, lightweight, solid reflector systems, Composite Optics, Incorporated (COI), was selected by Aerojet Electronic Systems Division (AESD) to develop the SSMIS reflector. To address the deployment mechanism detail development, COI teamed with Astro Aerospace Corporation (AAC), an international corporation highly recognized for its expertise in mechanism technology.

2. DESIGN

2.1 General The SSMIS deployable reflector is an offset 20-inch focal length paraboloid reflector with a 24-inch diameter aperture supported from a rotating base that slowly spins the system during operation. For the stowed, launch-phase configuration, the reflector is supported only by the deployment hinge mechanisms (2), and the mid-support arm release mechanisms (2). Similarly, the reflector is supported in the deployed, operational configuration by only the deployment hinge mechanisms and their lock features. The physical interfaces are taken to be at

FIGURE 2. THE SSMIS REFLECTOR

TABLE 1

MATERIAL PROPERTY SUMMARY
PSEUDOISOTROPIC P75/ERL1962

E (MSI)	=	14.2
G (MSI)	=	5.37
ν	=	0.32
α (PPM/F)	=	0.0 \pm 0.1 (-.10)
ρ (PCI)	=	0.065
F ^{TU} (KSI)	=	40.7 (30-32B-BASIS)
F ^{CU} (KSI)	=	22.2 (B-BASIS)
F ^{SU} (KSI)	=	20.8 (B-BASIS)
β (PPM/%M)	=	164.4
M _{MAX}	=	0.00108 (RH) ¹⁻⁴⁹

FIGURE 3. REFLECTOR COMPONENTS

the lower pivot points where the support deployment hinge mechanisms connect to the rotating base plate and at the mid-support arm points where the release mechanisms are mounted.

The deployable reflector, as presented in this paper, consists primarily of the following graphite/epoxy and mechanism components (shown in Figure 3):

- (1) Parabolic reflective shell
- (2) Support ring
- (3) Support arms (2)
- (4) Deployment hinge mechanisms (2)
- (5) Release mechanisms (2)

Each component has distinct functional and/or dimensional requirements.

2.2 Material Selection Candidate materials for the parabolic reflective shell, support ring, and support arms were evaluated on their merits for the best combination of high mechanical properties, stable thermal/hygrothermal performance, low mass properties, availability of mechanical/thermal/hygroscopic data base, and availability of heritage, background/reliability data. The selected material system was Amoco's P75S/ERL1962 graphite/epoxy unidirectional tape in the 1K tow fiber size (cured ply thickness = 0.0018 inch). The thinner fiber was selected because of its higher fiber surface area to cross-sectional area ratio which minimizes the thermal strain energy at the fiber surface interface with the matrix. This minimizes/eliminates the microcracking phenomenon over the operating temperature of this reflector. It also allows the use of thinner, minimum-gage pseudoisotropic lay-ups on the shell and support ring details, thus minimizing the reflector system weight. Using this material in a six-ply pseudoisotropic configuration was considered, but was determined to have the potential for microcracking and orthotropic properties in the minimum gages, thus jeopardizing the reflective surface accuracy. An eight-ply lay-up (0/45/90/135)_s was selected. COI utilized the mechanical stiffnesses and strengths and the thermal/hygroscopic properties indicated in Table 1.

2.3 Reflector Design

2.3.1 Reflective Surface The reflective surface is a thin, parabolic-shaped membrane of P75S/ERL1962 pseudoisotropic laminate. It is cured on a high-precision parabolic production mold to maintain the 0.0010-inch RMS surface accuracy in the center area ("sweet spot") and 0.0015 inch RMS surface accuracy around the perimeter area. The cured laminate thickness is 0.014 inch.

The reflective surface is prepared with a combination primer/Cabosil coating to reduce the surface specularity without compromising the surface accuracy. A vacuum deposited aluminum (VDA) coating is applied to the reflective surface for continuous electrical conductivity and overcoated with a silicon dioxide layer for corrosive protection and durability.

The reflective surface shape is maintained once it is removed from the production mold, assembled, tested, and transported to orbit by a perimeter support ring. The ring acts as a membrane edge stiffener while the shaped membrane settles into the

configuration of least stress (the precision parabolic contour) and transfers the reflector loads from the shell to the deployment arms. The support ring is a double-walled geometry with a cap, thus giving it a pi shape. The interfacing edges of the ring walls are contoured to an offset parabola and mated to the reflective surface shell doublers. Intercostals inside the ring cross-section are incorporated to maintain shear strength. All ring details utilize the minimum pseudoisotropic material thickness of 0.014 inch with minimal areas on the cap detail increasing to .028 inch for stiffness.

2.3.2 **Deployment Arms** The deployment arms are the supporting members between the deployment mechanisms and the reflective surface which also integrate the release mechanisms into the reflector assembly. They are a critical detail that affects the reflector system modal frequencies in the stowed configuration, the beam pointing error in the deployed configuration and the repeatability of the focal point location during multiple deployments. The arm's cross-section is 2.39-inch x 1.39-inch x .060-inch thick and is a P75S/ERL1962 pseudoisotropic lay-up. Clearance openings and reinforcing bulkheads are incorporated at the mid-arm location for the release mechanism details. Gusset plates and reinforcing shear clips are incorporated at each end detail for interfacing with the support ring and deployment hinge mechanisms.

2.3.3 **Deployment Mechanisms** The deployment movement of the reflector assembly from the stowed position to the operational deployed position is about a hinge axis at the bottom of the two support arms. This movement is controlled by two different details, the deployment hinge mechanism and the release mechanism. The details were designed, analyzed, fabricated and qualified by COI's major subcontractor, Astro Aerospace Corporation.

2.4 **Mass Properties** The weight of the reflector assembly is 7.62 lbs., 5.26 lbs. of which is the four mechanism details. The remaining 2.36 lbs. is divided between the reflective shell (1.03 lbs.) and the deployment arms (1.33 lbs.). The areal density of 1.8 kg/sq. meter for this reflector is less than 50% of nominal sandwich construction shell/support rib arrangements and 85% of previous membrane construction shell/support rib designs.

3. STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

3.1 **Modeling Technique** The reflector assembly was designed to meet the structural, thermal, and configurational requirements shown in Figure 4.

To meet these requirements and assure adequate margins-of-safety for strength and stability (mechanical, thermal) considerations, a detailed finite element model of the reflector assembly was developed.

The structural assembly was modeled using PDA/Patran Plus, and subsequently analyzed using Version 66A of MSC/Nastran. The reflector surface, rear stiffener ring and deployment arms (2) were modeled via plate elements, while the deployment mechanisms (2) were modeled via a combi-

nation of plate and solid elements. External components, such as pin-puller assemblies, optical cube, and thermal blankets were represented via lumped masses. The final model consisted of a total of 1,746 grid points, 1,534 plates, 212 solids, 2 spring elements, and 190 lumped masses. A detailed representation of the reflector assembly finite element model is presented in Figure 5.

A complete summary of the various loading conditions that were analyzed under the current program is presented below:

- Modal frequency -- stowed and deployed configuration
- Random vibration analysis
 - All three axes independently
- Shock analyses
 - Spacecraft loads
 - Reflector deployment
- Quasi-static accelerations
 - Launch loads
 - 1-G alignment
- Thermal stress/distortion analysis
- Hygroscopic analysis
- Deployment analysis
- Stability analysis
 - Mechanical -- buckling
 - Thermal -- pointing accuracies
- Detailed bondline/fitting analysis

While detailed analyses were conducted for each of the aforementioned loading conditions, modal frequency (stiffness), random vibration (stress), and thermal distortion (optical pointing) requirements were the most difficult to meet and are discussed later.

- Thermal
 - Survival temperature range -85°C/+93°C
 - Operational thermal pointing accuracy ≤ 0.001 in. RMS
 - Hygrothermal distortions ≤ 0.001 in. RMS
- Structural
 1. Natural frequency
 - Stowed ≥ 120 Hz
 - Deployed ≥ 25 Hz
 2. Random vibration spectrum .27 g²/Hz (30-1500 Hz)
22.3 grms
 3. Shock spectrum Pyroshock
 4. Acoustic spectrum 141 dB overall sound pressure
 5. Quasi-static launch loads ± 30 g's per axis
 6. 1-g pointing accuracy ≤ 0.010R F.P. distortion
 7. Deployment repeatability ≤ 0.010R F.P. distortion
 8. Fabrication tolerances ≤ .001 in. RMS

FIGURE 4. THE SSMIS REFLECTOR PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS

FIGURE 5. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL OF THE SSMIS REFLECTOR

3.2 Modal Frequency Modal frequency requirements for each of the stowed and deployed configurations are presented in Figure 4. Numerous design iterations were conducted to optimize the structure from a stiffness-to-mass standpoint. This parametric study indicated that, while minimal weight savings could be obtained by tapering the backside stiffener ring, the relative importance of maintaining a stiff deployment arm-to-reflector surface joint is crucial to meet current stiffness requirements.

Initial design configurations assumed that both stowed and deployed tie-down configurations occurred at the mechanism-to-canister interfaces. Thus, the relative stiffnesses of the deployment arm and the mechanism were very important. However, when the stowed stiffness requirements continued to increase, the need for two additional tie-down locations on the deployment arms became necessary. Thus, the influence of the mechanism and deployment arm stiffnesses were greatly reduced, and additional mass saving was obtained. The amount of mass saving (i.e. stiffness reduction) was limited, however, due to the 1-G alignment requirements necessary to be performed on the reflector assembly while in the deployed configuration. The final locations of the tie-downs on the deployment arms were obtained via coupled loads analyses conducted at the system level (i.e., decoupling of modes between the reflector assembly and canister).

Eigenvalue extractions were performed using the Modified Givens method option of MSC/Nastran. Mode shapes were normalized to a unit generalized mass for consistency. A summary of the first three natural frequencies for both the stowed and deployed configurations is as follows:

f_1 (stowed)	=	115.2 Hz	f_1 (deployed)	=	44.5 Hz
f_2 (stowed)	=	179.6 Hz	f_2 (deployed)	=	51.6 Hz
f_3 (stowed)	=	228.0 Hz	f_3 (deployed)	=	75.2 Hz

3.3 Random Vibration Analyses Stresses induced in the reflector assembly due to the random vibration spectrum defined in Figure 4 resulted in the highest predicted stresses throughout the structure. Application of the random vibration spectrum to the structure was accomplished via base excitations. The canister interface was assumed to be infinitely rigid. A structural damping factor of 1.5% of critical damping was assumed and considered conservative based on previous programs. The critical stresses were in the reflector support ring at the support arms, but generally were significantly lower in all other structural members.

3.4 Thermal Stress/Distortion Analysis On-orbit performance requirements for the reflector assembly were governed by thermal loading conditions. An RMS surface accuracy of ≤ 0.001 inches for the inner 8.0-inch radius of the reflector surface was required for operational conditions. A total of four (4) temperature distributions representing the various orbital conditions were integrated into the finite element model. A summary of the corresponding best-fit surface analyses is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2. RMS SURFACE ANALYSIS SUMMARY

LOAD CASE	DESCRIPTION	BEST-FIT FOCAL LENGTH (inches)	BEST-FIT RMS	FOCAL POINT ERROR
1A	HALF-SUN	20.0015	.101-4	.005
1B	HALF-SHADOW	20.0	.19-3	.0099
2A	-130°F	19.9905	.347-4	.017
2B		20.0	.0028	.0099-4
3A	+10°F	20.0026	.128-4	.0064
3B	SIDE-TO-SIDE	20.0	.26-3	0.01
4A	+60°F GRADIENT	20.0022	.119-4	.0058
4B	FRONT-TO-FRONT	20.0	.259-3	.01

- *Combined thermal + hygroscopic*
- *60% R.H. → dry condition*
- *Thermal/hygroscopic cases added linearly*

4.0 FABRICATION

4.1 Tooling As it has on several previous programs, COI utilized "proven concept" tooling to generate and measure the accuracy of the precision parabolic surface to close tolerances. The following major tools were developed and utilized on this program:

- (1) Precision parabolic production mold (PDMO)
- (2) Support ring subassembly fixture
- (3) Final assembly fixture

4.1.1 Production Mold (PDMO) Specific to this reflector configuration and its surface accuracy requirements, COI had a bulk graphite precision male parabolic PDMO fabricated. It was the most critical element in the reflector production

process. The parabolic PDMO had the following characteristics:

- (1) Complete temporal dimensional stability after machining; i.e., zero creep-relaxation, hygroscopic or thermal-cycling changes.
- (2) Coefficient of thermal expansion matching the reflector shell material.
- (3) High resistance to deterioration with repeated use.
- (4) High stiffness-to-density.
- (5) Very high-precision accuracy after multiple thermal cycles simulating many cure cycles (Table 3).

TABLE 3
BEST FIT CONTOUR PLOTS FOR SSMIS REFLECTOR PRODUCTION MOLD TOOLING

	BEST FIT RMS VALUES					
	NO. OF PTS.	RMS *	NO. OF PTS.	RMS **	NO. OF PTS.	RMS ***
ALL DATA	316	0.00126	316	0.00121	316	0.000838
0 < R < 8	129	0.000632	129	0.00056	129	0.000415
8 < R < 12	158	0.00099	158	0.000905	162	0.000662

* Assumes focal length fixed at 20 inches

** Graphite PDMO cycled 10 times from RT to +350°F

*** RMS data includes compensation for 3mm diameter measuring ball

Tooling holes were positioned on the parabolic PDMO surface and transferred to the composite shell after cure. These holes were used to establish the coordinates of the reference point used as part of the best-fit calculations for surface measurements during final assembly and testing. The support arm tubes and angle stock were laid up and cured on male production molds fabricated from solid aluminum bar stock. The aluminum tools were fabricated with part springback and tool CTE differential allowances built in.

- 4.1.2 Subassembly and Final Assembly Fixtures Two major tooling fixtures were designed and fabricated by COI and used appropriately to control the location of elements during critical assembly operations: the back support ring assembly fixture and the final assembly fixture. The back support ring assembly fixture was used to position the back support ring elements relative to one another during the ring subassembly. The support ring elements were hand-fit to hard points in the tooling and used as bonding assembly tools. The final assembly fixture was used to position and secure the subassembled reflector shell/supporting details in their nominal positions while the focal point (along with the deployment hinge mechanism) was positioned to the relative best-fit position and attitude with respect to the measured parabolic surface. The reflector surface was positioned using the tooling ball locations. The deployment arms were incorporated between the reflector support ring and the deployment hinge mechanism in this fixture.

4.2 Manufacturing COI refined their manufacturing processes and procedures that it had developed and utilized successfully on the RCA Direct Broadcast Satellite (DBS) Deployable Reflector (84" aperture) in 1983 and applied them to fabricate this reflector. The major fabrication tasks were: a) lay up of parabolic shell, support tubes, and flatstock; b) ring assembly; and, c) final reflector assembly.

4.2.1 Lay-up The reflector shell was laid up in a pseudoisotropic orientation of minimum thickness and autoclave cured on a graphite PDMO with a rubber overpress. Flatstock skins for the ring walls, intercostals, and cap were laid up in a pseudoisotropic orientation of minimum thickness and autoclave cured.

4.2.2 Assembly All back support ring details were trimmed from the thin flatstock, hand-fit within the subassembly fixture, and bonded with Hysol EA9394 epoxy. The unitized support structure was then thermal cycled prior to contouring the interfacing edges to the parabolic shell profile. After successfully fit-checking the ring profile at the interface, the ring and the parabolic shell were bonded together on the parabolic PDMO.

The final assembly was completed on the fixture that coordinated and secured the relative position of the best-fit parabola to the fixed focal point and the deployment hinge mechanism. With both the reflector shell and deployment hinge mechanism positioned, the support arms were bonded to both mating interfaces. The reflector assembly was rotated from the deployed position to the stowed attitude where the release mechanisms were installed in the deployment arms at the mid-support location to match the release interface surface.

A vacuum deposited aluminum (VDA) coating was applied to the precision parabolic surface to provide a continuous conductive interface for RF considerations. The VDA coating consists of layers of chromium, aluminum and SiO_2 for the proper adhesion to the P75S/ERL1962 shell interface, solar absorptivity, and thermal emissivity.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

The SSMIS reflector design presented here is the result of an effort to optimize the mechanical, thermal, and mass characteristics of a high-precision, high-performance space environment reflector through the application of current graphite/epoxy materials. This reflector design is expected to meet all performance requirements of the DMSP mission. The electrical characteristics of the SSMIS engineering model as tested by Aerojet Electronic Systems Division have shown excellent agreement between predicted and measured values over the SSMIS frequency spectrum. The electrical performance, which includes half-power beam width, beam efficiency, beam pointing, and radiation pattern measurements, verified the high-precision integrity of the reflector. All electrical requirements, including the 183 GHz channel, have satisfied or surpassed the predicted performance. A full series of mechanical and thermal deployment tests for development and qualification reflector units are scheduled for the April/May and August through October 1991

time frame. Based on conservative analysis approaches and COI's past experience of reflector programs, we feel that all customer performance requirements will be met or exceeded in the testing phase.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Gary A. Tremblay, a design engineer and program manager at Composite Optics, Incorporated, receive his BSCE degree from the University of Cincinnati in 1973 and MSCE from Colorado State University in 1974. He has 13 years experience in designing aerospace structural systems. Recently, he was the program manager and lead design engineer for the development and production of a graphite/epoxy deployable reflector for the SSMIS. His prior composite design and program management included was on several reflectors (SATCOM, GSTAR, DBS, and Superbird); as well as spacecraft structures (ACTS and Telstar).

Ed Derby is Director of Engineering and has over 15 years of experience in the analysis of composite structures. In December, 1982, Mr. Derby joined COI's engineering staff where he assumed responsibility for the application and expansion of analytical capabilities in the area of thermally stable structures.

During Mr. Derby's eight years at COI, he has provided structural analysis support on over six parabolic reflector programs, four optical benches, three telescope metering structures, a camera housing, and a number of other composite components designed, fabricated and tested at COI.

Prior to joining COI, Mr. Derby was a member of Materials Sciences Corporation (MSC) engineering staff and, prior to that, was employed as a stress engineer at the McDonnell-Douglas Astronautics Company.

Mr. Derby has authored or co-authored several papers related to the effects of moisture absorption on the mechanical properties of composite materials.

